

Rhizosphere modelling to advance crop breeding strategies

Problem

When breeding crops for resilience to abiotic stress it can be challenging to determine the effect of a specific trait on plant performance, particularly for traits of the root system and rhizosphere. Mathematical models could be used to address this issue.

Solution

Using genotypic and environmental data, models can be developed that not only show the growth of the root systems but also how their activity modifies the surrounding soil environment.

Benefits

These models can predict the ability of certain genotypes to withstand an abiotic stress. For example, the capacity of root systems to maximise water uptake during periods of limited water supply.

Practical recommendations

- Simulate root system growth using a root system architecture model, and construct the corresponding root length density functions (Figure 1).
- Use experimental data to predict rhizodeposit distribution around plant roots and determine the effect on soil properties like water retention, hydraulic conductivity and microbial activity.
- Develop models for soil water transport and root water uptake that incorporate rhizodeposit effects and show the impact on soil water dynamics (Figure 2).
- Use simulations to analyse how the expression of given traits (e.g. root architecture, rhizodeposit type) affects crop performance under a range of soil types and climatic conditions (Figure 3).
- The application of the models will require modifications to the crop simulation platforms currently used by professionals to inform crop management (e.g. irrigation, fertiliser application, etc.).
- The main difficulty is obtaining data for the effect on soil hydraulics of rhizodeposits from different crop genotypes. This is required to calibrate models and thus reliably predict crop performance.

Applicability box

Theme: Resistance to abiotic stress in crops

Keywords: Mathematical modelling, rhizodeposition, microbiome, soil, water uptake, rhizosphere

Context: Predict performance of crop ideotypes

Application time: All year

Required time: 1-year software development for introduction in crop model platform (e.g. aquacrop, Apsim)

Period of impact: 5 years

Equipment: Computer, suitable software (FEniCS, Python3, CPlantBox, CRootBox), algorithms (density function construction) and relevant data (root architecture data in tabular form and parameters obtained from literature)

Best in: All cropping systems where data is available to calibrate a model

Figure 1: Root system architecture generated with CRootBox software (left). Corresponding root length density profile (right).

Figure 2: Simulation of soil water dynamics with rhizodeposits (red border) and without (blue border).

Figure 3: The effect of rhizodeposits on root water uptake under different rainfall patterns: total rainfall delivered on day 1 (left); total rainfall split between day 1 and day 3 (right).

Further information

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About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils.

Project website: root2res.eu

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